

Pipeline Theory: Performative Spirituality Produces Bastardized Children of the Church

Maman Ruh | Hoodoo Church: The Conjure Haus | Conjure Worx de la Ruh

There is a crisis unfolding inside my community, one that i feel can no longer be ignored or tolerated. With this paper I set the intention that this conversation will spark the needed worxs that will begin to seal the gaping holes of division between each other. What is unfolding moves beneath the surface of what appears to take on the silhouette of growth. With it we see the influx of new practitioners, new platforms, new products, new visibility and it appears to be producing quietly and steadily. But beneath that surface, a condition is breeding that will cause a deeper severance than anything colonialism accomplished through direct prohibition. Once upon a time, colonial power succeeded in destroying Black spiritual traditions through force and assimilation. Now consumer capitalism is absorbing it through aestheticization. The result will be a people cut off from consciousness completely, severed from connection within their own community. The living root of their own knowing, corrupted without a reversal.

I am writing this as a practitioner, a prophetic teacher, and the founder of The Hoodoo Church: The Conjure Haus. I am not writing about these practices from a distance. I am writing from inside it, with accountability to the communities this work serves. What I am naming here I have watched unfold in real time across digital spiritual spaces, inside communities, and inside the lives of people who came to these practices looking for the source of our rootz and found a marketplace instead. This paper names that marketplace and it will name what it costs us. And it names the specific mechanism by which the people most equipped to carry and transmit that Black spiritual heritage are being converted, one performance at a time, into spectacles and what happens when the spectacle collapses?

THE EPISTEMOLOGICAL INHERITANCE

Before we can understand what is being lost, we have to be clear about what we are talking about. The Black diasporic has birthed many spiritual traditions like Hoodoo, Conjure, Moorish Science, the prophetic Black church, black spirituals just to name a few all those roots are found here in America. Vodou forged on the battlefield of Ayiti, Candomble and Umbanda mastered in Brazil, Santeria and all across the Caribbean. If you have the mind of God you will see before you just a small epistemological system that exist within the cultures of Black People. Scholars like Albert Raboteau, Zora Neale Hurston, Stephanie Mitchem, Anthony Pinn, and Theophus Smith have documented the coherence and depth of Black American spiritual life as a tradition forged on this soil not merely preserved from Africa but transformed through specific historical conditions into something sovereign and irreducible. Hurston's fieldwork documented Hoodoo in real time, she had a way of extracting the superstition while curating a systematic knowledgeable blueprint she could physically give back to us. Through her writings she taught us a different way of reading the natural world, working with plant and animal intelligence, while maintaining our relationship with the unseen in service of the living community.

Out traditions answered the foundational questions of existence on its own terms. How do we understand our relationship to God, to Source, to the animating force of all things? How do we read the natural world? How do we commune with the earth and its creatures? How do we locate ourselves within this divine Universe? How do we protect our children, heal our sick, honor our dead, and move through suffering without being destroyed by it? I don't want these questions to land as peripheral questions, I want them to be what builds the architecture of your consciousness. And it is precisely this architecture that performative spirituality dismantles leaving the aesthetic surface intact while gutting your entire interior.

I want to be very clear about something that is often lost in these conversations: Black Americans spiritual heritage is not just an afterthought of a subset of African tradition. Let me say that again. Black Americans spiritual heritage is not just an afterthought of a subset of African tradition. It is its own

sovereign body of knowledge. Full Stop. Our workings were forged here, under specific conditions, through specific genius and specific suffering. Hoodoo is American. The spirituals are American. The prophetic Black church is American. At the same time, the broader diaspora across Africa, the Caribbean, Brazil, and beyond carries its own complete traditions that must be honored on their own terms. The full inheritance is vast. All of it is under pressure, none of it should be reducible to any other.

CAPITALISM CONVERTS YOUR LONGING INTO A SPECTACLE

Consumer capitalism is extraordinarily efficient at converting genuine longing into purchasing power for all who desire to profit. What we are seeing within the collective is what I want to define as Spiritual hunger. A very real legitimate necessity for connection with Source, with the earth, with our ancestors and with our community. But this longing is disappearing under late stage capitalism. To me it intensifies, particularly among our communities for whom the dominant culture's institutions have historically offered violence and dismissal rather than transcendence. That intensified longing becomes a marketplace for the capture of knowledge and power.

Guy Debord's provides an analysis of this spectacle calling it the displacement of lived experience by its representation. I unfortunately see this specific and devastating application within the digital spiritual culture today. The altar that photographs well replaces the altar that actually functions. The rituals are performed for an audience replacing the privacy our ritual spaces required, disrupting your relationship with the living forces around you. The center of gravity shifts from practice to power point presentation, from the gaze of the divine to the gaze of the crowd. This is aesthetic degradation. It is a fundamental inversion of the purpose and direction of spiritual work.

Social media platforms accelerates and entrenches this inversion with algorithms that reward consistency of persona, emotional amplification, and audience engagement. The practitioner learns immediately what performs and what doesn't. The feedback loop takes over, genuine practice become slow, difficult, and resistant to documentation. Those with real practices gets starved of space while the performative version expands to fill the platform. Eventually the content about the practice displaces the practice itself. You stop having a practice and start producing content about said practice. The altar become the Golden Calf while the river runs red with our blood and attention. Bell hooks' analysis of the commodification of Blackness is instructive here. When Black cultural and spiritual expression is converted into a consumable product, what reaches the marketplace is typically a flattened, decontextualized version of your works stripped of its historical weight, its political charge, its relational obligations, and its demands. The aesthetic remains. The epistemology is discarded. Thus creating the spirituality of accumulation, be it crystals, decks, tools, courses, certifications each one promising completion yet none of these modalities have delivered it, can you see it's by design yet?

THE CARICATURE BEFORE ME

There is a specific violence that performative spirituality does to the individual practitioner that does not get named clearly enough in this climate. It forces you to turn yourself into a caricature of yourself. You are required to become a spectacle, a louder, flattened version of your actual practice and you must maintain that spectacle continuously in order to hold your audience. It starts subtly. You share something genuine, it lands, people respond. And then, almost imperceptibly, the feedback loop takes over. You start adjusting you are no longer sharing your actual practice anymore you are producing an algorithm out of your practice. Fuck the audience at that point, all you'll be left with is a flesh signal but no substance will be found within you.

The audience becomes a master you did not agree to serve. And the cruelest part is the intimacy of illusion. Your followers feel like they know you, feel entitled to your energy, they begin to feel like your humanness belongs to them. You become indebted to your audience, so when you try to pull back so that you can protect something sacred refusing to perform will read as betrayal to the people who boosted your fame. The caricature must keep performing or the whole thing collapses. This is your shucking and jiving ministry. And for Black and brown practitioners specifically, it carries the full

historical weight of that phrase. The dynamic in which Black practitioners must perform their sacred identity for audiences that frequently consume without reciprocity is not a new configuration. It echoes throughout this minstrel economy, in which Black performance was required to be accessible and entertaining to be tolerated in white-dominated commercial spaces.

HIGH VIBRATIONS WHILE THE BLOOD ACCUMULATES

Performative spirituality does not only distort practice. It functions as a dissociation mechanism. The emphasis on positive frequency, spiritual ascension, and aesthetic transcendence operates to insulate practitioners from the weight of the material reality happening around them. This is what is called spiritual bypassing in its most culturally sophisticated form. You use spiritual frameworks to avoid your shadow of suffering rather than engage the full range of communal experience which includes suffering, grief, rage, and political emergency. We are neck deep in blood right now. No we are up to our waist deep in blood, walking through rivers of discarded people geopolitically and ecologically. In the ongoing normalization of anti-Black violence and the erasure of Black suffering from public consciousness. And across the landscape of Black spiritual and cultural life, people who should be seers, intercessors, and rootworkers are maintaining personas, building audiences, and blaming planetary alignments for your bad behavior and misalignment. Operating within that framework is not the transcendence you teach of, you are teaching dissociation as ascension.

Black diasporic spiritual traditions were never designed for dissociation. The spirituals were not comfort music that helped enslaved people forget their condition, they were coded communication, collective prayer, and maps to freedom. Conjure was not aesthetic practice it was protection, resistance, and survival technology. Black liberation theology insisted that God's action in history was on the side of the oppressed and demanded engagement. When this tradition is replaced by the prostitution of spirituality that counsels aesthetic withdrawal, the community loses its prophetic function. The blood continues to accumulate, and the people most equipped to call it forward are busy managing their feeds or battling who's the real deal within these communities. The question that must be asked of any spiritual practice in this moment is simple "Can you still breathe?" Not does your altar photograph well. Not how many followers do you have. Can you still breathe? meaning, can you feel the weight of what is happening around you? Can you sit in the blood without aestheticizing it? Can you hold the grief and the urgency of the collective without without turning a blind eye for the betterment of your social platforms? In what ways have your initiations shifted the planet outside of your pockets? What purpose does initiations serve if the conditions of the community is sick while everyone turns a profit or increases fame?

PERFORMATIVE SPIRITUALITY PRODUCES BASTARDIZED CHILDREN OF THE CHURCH

Bastardized Children of the Church, meaning when you preform your way through these spiritual systems created by our people without doing the deconstructing of your church or religious mind, you create a corrupted lineage producing the foundation for an incomplete inheritance. There is a specific cycle that performative spirituality produces, and it is one of the most consequential dynamics inside Black spiritual communities and churches right now. When a person enters Black diasporic spiritual practices through the door of the aesthetic, through the appeal of the visual, the communal energy of social media, the identity of the desire of becoming a practitioner but you never develop genuine rootedness within the tradition, you are building on sand. You are spiritually prostituting. You will sink just as the church is sinking now. Performative spiritual practices never addresses the actual conditions of a person's life. It aestheticizes over chaos with no real goal of resolving it. Accumulation becomes the goal until you as as decorated as the pastor sitting in the ruins of his or her own congregation. So when life becomes difficult or down right unjust and it will the practice or church will offer nothing solid to truly stand on. Leaving the young spiritualist to run back to the safety of the church to repent of their sins. And the cycle of the demonization of African based spiritual systems take their place in landing you back in hell. The crystals do not hold the center. The content does not provide the ground. And the chaos that was always there, that was never actually worked on, is still awaiting you. Religion can only mask what you refuse to face Sinnerman.

At that moment, Christianity particularly Black Christianity, which is deeply communally embedded, emotionally resonant, and culturally familiar will offer a ready structure for you at the exchange of you back in chains. It has a language for the chaos around you. It has community. It has a framework for sin, deliverance and redemption that makes sense of suffering. That is not nothing. It is genuinely compelling when you are unmoored. And so people return. But here is what must be understood this return happens not because the ancestral practice failed. It happens because the person was never actually rooted within their ancestral practice. They were performing it and collecting applause, unfortunately performance has no root system to sustain you. Don't wait til midnight for what's unrooted in you to fail you, your tradition won't be on trial your performance will be. We must abandon the performative imitation of limitations within our traditions.

The demonization layer amplifies this, and this is where the real damage to the community occurs to me. Once someone returns to the church in that vulnerable state, the African-based practice they came from frequently gets reframed in the retelling as the source of the chaos. It becomes witchcraft. It becomes demonic. The tradition that failed them was not the ancestral practice, it was the commercialization of Christianity that taught spiritual performance. We were groomed into loving the vision of the God of the west through submission. You who abandon and demonize you ancestral spiritual systems after or before you have tasted the fruits of them never fully entered through acceptance but through the pain of your rebellion and so returning feels like relief, and that distinction between the two collapses again. You reassign your deconstruction as the problem abandon the tradition itself, and assign the Gods of the west your salvation again.

That narrative then travels into family, into community, into social media and it becomes another barrier, another layer of suspicion and fear, for the next person considering genuine engagement with their ancestral heritage. The colonial project of demonizing African-based spiritual systems is older than the Middle Passage, fueled not primarily from outside the community but from people within it, from people who look like me, from practitioners who entered through the aesthetic door, from your pulpits and what's left behind is performative practices, chaos, migrations back to Christianity, the demonization of the traditions and more people being blocked from genuine rootedness within the linages we come from. It is self-perpetuating cycle and it serves, whether anyone intends it to or not, the same function that direct colonial prohibition served, keeping Black people estranged from the full power of their own spiritual inheritance.

CLASSISM AND THE MONETIZATION OF SACRED KNOWLEDGE

A dimension of the commodification crisis that receives insufficient attention is the classism it generates within Black spiritual communities as sacred knowledge becomes a premium product courses, certifications, paid readings, high-cost initiations economic access becomes the primary filter for spiritual legitimacy. In communities already economically stressed by centuries of structural racism, this dynamic has serious consequences. It is important to distinguish between appropriate structures of transmission and exploitative gatekeeping. Traditional initiation systems carry real costs and time, relationship, commitment, and material investment and these costs are not arbitrary. They reflect the weight and responsibility of what is being transmitted. The concern is not initiation itself but the specific distortion that occurs when economic access becomes the primary criterion for spiritual advancement, and when sacred knowledge is repackaged as scalable digital product for broad commercial sale.

The social media status layer compounds this. Elaborate altar setups, expensive tools, multiple initiations, and access to high-profile teachers become visible markers of spiritual authority in digital spaces markers that are, at their root, markers of class position. This replicates within spiritual community the exact hierarchies the tradition was designed to transcend. Those who cannot afford access get positioned as less developed, less legitimate, less worthy. The fractures generated by these dynamics between the initiated and uninitiated, between those who can afford access and those who cannot, between African, Caribbean, and American diaspora practitioners arguing over authenticity are not organic disagreements within a

healthy tradition. They are wounds created by outside interference and by the internal adoption of corrupted frameworks. The division is a consequence of the distortion. And it serves, as all such divisions serve, the interests of those who benefit from Black communities remaining fragmented and estranged from their own power.

This paper has argued that performative spirituality severs the Black community from an inherited epistemological system. This has political consequences as well, Black diasporic spiritual traditions were expanded and forced to evolve and in some respects devolve under enslavement to birth new survival technologies. It was the only way my people endured conditions designed to destroy their humanity, how they encoded resistance, how they maintained collective identity across forced dispersal, and how they sustained the prophetic capacity to name injustice and call for liberation. The conjure practitioner protected. The elder who read the signs warned. The church at its most prophetic organized. These were not separate from political life but the spiritual infrastructure of political resistance. When that infrastructure is displaced by performative spirituality, the community loses precisely those functions. The prophetic voice gets converted into content we approve or disapprove of. Our protective practice becomes aesthetics people consume. The communal discernment that historically allowed Black communities to read the political landscape through a spiritual lens dissipate and the most powerful of our communities get denied replaced by individualized, consumption-oriented spiritual people, beliefs and practices that reinforces our oppression rather than disrupt the existing order.

A community practicing performative spirituality cannot fully see what is happening. Because performative spirituality is, in its function, a dissociation mechanism. It aestheticizes the crisis rather than engaging it. And a dissociated community is an easier community to manage, to disappear and to render complicit to its own suffering. The normalization of Black Death and shady politics and the normalization of performative spirituality are not unrelated phenomena. They are sending us in the same looping direction. The practitioners turned entrepreneurs, the platform economy, the new-age adjacent market that absorbs Black spiritual aesthetics while the originators get priced out of their own tradition. Economic gatekeeping matters most in our traditions specifically because these traditions were designed to transmit information through relationship, proximity, and time not through buying ability. When you commodify that, you don't just create classism, you destroy our actual vehicle of transmission.

The counter to performative spirituality is not a retreat from sharing knowledge, building community, or engaging the public. It is a fundamental reorientation of purpose and accountability. Grounded practice asks different questions than performative practice asks. Not: how does this look? But: am I in actual relationship with the forces I claim to work with? Not: how many people are watching? But: am I accountable to a community, not just an audience? Not: does this affirm me? But: does this demand something of me in discipline, in sacrifice, in communal obligation?

Our traditions know what they are here for, It has always known, it is you who is lost. Our systems brought us the power of survival under impossible conditions. It was for maintaining the relationship between Black people and God, earth, cosmos, and each other through every attempt to sever those relationships. It was for keeping the community's eyes open when the dominant culture demanded its blindness. It was for the living. For reclaiming our spiritual heritage. Our traditions are not formed from the marketplace it is a spiritual act. It is a political one. Genuine rootedness in our very Black spiritual heritage demands real practice, real relationship, real accountability, and real sacrifice. For this is one of the most subversive things a Black person can pursue today. Not the aesthetic. Not the content. The practice. Not the performance. The actual, living, demanding, protective, prophetic thing itself. The blood has accumulated. The question is whether enough people can still breathe to do something about it.

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